

Fig. 1

Experimental

(II) β -Aryl- γ -Aroyl-Butyric Acid :

A mixture of KOH (0.657 g, 0.012 M), diethyl malonate (4.2 g, 0.03 M), ethanol (1 ml), ether (10 ml) were placed in a 250 ml round bottom flask, equipped with a dropping funnel, a mechanical stirrer and a cooling bath. The mixture was stirred at 15° and chalcone⁶ (0.015 M) in 100 ml of ether was added dropwise over 1 hr. It was further stirred for additional 2.5 hrs at room temperature. Then the mixture was acidified with dil. HCl and the ether layer was separated. The residue after removing the solvent was diluted with KOH solution (5.3 g in 10 ml of H₂O) to give deformed mass, which was heated on steam bath for 2 hrs (10 ml of water was added at the end of 1 hr). It was then cooled under tap and conc. H₂SO₄ (9 g in 12 ml of H₂O) was added slowly (cracking noise and white ppt.). The mixture was heated on steam bath for 3 hrs, cooled under tap and extracted with saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (30 ml). The heterogeneous aqueous layer after acidification gave white ppt. which was recrystallized from boiling water.

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Synthesis of 1-formyl-8-hydroxycarbazole

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THE formyl carbazoles have recently figured prominently in carbazole alkaloids¹ as well as an intermediate in the synthesis of pyridocarbazoles of potential antitumour activity^{2,3}. Synthesis of carbazole aldehydes was first reported by Buu Hoi *et al*⁴, in 1951 and later by Tomlinson *et al*⁵, in 1957. Since there is no convenient and good method for the synthesis of formyl carbazoles, the present work for the synthesis of formyl carbazole was undertaken.

Chakraborty *et al*⁶, synthesised successfully many simple and complex carbazoles by Borsche method in conjunction with Japp-Klingemann reaction. Recently DDQ has been used to obtain formyl carbazoles from carbazoles with aromatic C-Me groups^{7,1}. We now report the synthesis of 1-formyl-8-hydroxycarbazole in which DDQ^{8,9}, has been used to effect aromatisation of six-membered aromatic ring with allyl alcoholic system and oxidation of the carbinol group in a single step.

The starting material was cyclohexanone which on formylation with ethyl formate in presence of sodium ethoxide gave 2-formyl cyclohexanone(I) which on Japp-Klingemann reaction with diazotised methyl anthranilate(II) furnished cyclohexane 1,2-dione (1'-carbomethoxy)monophenylhydrazone(III). The hydrazone(III) was then cyclised by boiling with a mixture of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid when 1-carbomethoxy-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole(IV) was obtained, which on LAH reduction furnished the compound(V). Compound(V) on aromatisation and oxidation in a single step with DDQ furnished 1-formyl-8-hydroxycarbazole(VI). The method is schematically shown below :

Experimental

Preparation of cyclohexane 1,2-dione-(1'-carbomethoxy)-monophenylhydrazone(III) :

To a methanolic solution of 2-formyl cyclohexanone¹⁰ (12.6 g) a solution of sodium acetate (25 g) in water (50 ml) was added. To this solution a diazotised solution obtained from methyl ester of anthranilic acid (15.1 g) was gradually added for a period of forty minutes under mechanical agitation. The stirring was continued for two hours. The yellow precipitate formed was filtered and washed with water to make it acid free. The pure compound was obtained from the crude material by filtering through a column of basic alumina and eluting with benzene-chloroform mixture (5 : 1). It was crystallised from benzene and chloroform mixture when fine needle-shaped homogeneous crystals of the hydrazone(III), m.p. 164°, ν_{\max} (nujol) 3300, 1695, 1660, 1615, 1600, 1535 and 765 cm^{-1} , λ_{\max}

(EtOH) 220 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.6), 229 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.25) and 252 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.25), were obtained. Yield 80%.

Analytical Data :

Found : C, 64.61%, H, 6.15%, N, 10.77% Calcd. for : $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 64.5% ; H, 6.2% ; N, 10.75%.

Preparation of 1-carbomethoxy-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole(IV) :

The crude hydrazone (14 g) obtained in the previous step was added to boiling glacial acetic acid (65 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 ml) was added through the reflux condenser and the solution was boiled for 2-3 minutes. The solution was then poured into crushed ice (500 g) and stirred. On working up the reaction mixture, purification and crystallisation from chloroform-benzene mixture faint yellow coloured plate type heavy crystals of 1-carbomethoxy-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole(IV), m.p. 134-35°, ν_{\max} (nujol) 3560, 1720, 1690, 1640, 1610, 1580, 790 and 755 cm^{-1} and λ_{\max} (EtOH) 312 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.75), 271 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.1), 263 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.0) and 225 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.65), were obtained. The p.m.r. (90 MHz) spectrum of the compound in CDCl_3 showed the presence of two aliphatic protons at C_6 (δ 2.15-2.4, complex multiplet, 2H), two aliphatic protons at C_5 (δ 2.65, t, J=6Hz, 2H), two aliphatic protons at C_7 (δ 3.0, t, J=6Hz, 2H), protons of carbomethoxy group (δ 4.02, s, 3H), aromatic proton at C_4 (δ 7.22, d, J=8Hz, 1H), aromatic protons at C_2 and C_3 (δ 7.8-8.2, complex structure, 2H) and N-H proton (δ 10.1, broad singlet, 1H). Yield 60%.

Analytical data :

Found : C, 69.13% ; H, 5.35% ; N, 5.76% Calcd. for : $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}$: C, 69.2% ; H, 5.3% ; N, 5.72%.

Preparation of 1-carbinol-8-hydroxy-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole(V) :

Lithium aluminium hydride (500 mg) was added to dry ether in a two necked round-bottomed flask attached with a reflux condenser. It was stirred for about 15-20 minutes. To this pasty solution, a solution of the purified oxo-compound (2 g) in dry ether was added dropwise. After the addition was complete, the whole content was vigorously refluxed for 30 minutes. On working up the reaction mixture a white semisolid residue was obtained. Yield 70%. The spectral data of the compound are ν_{\max} (nujol) 3440, 1600, 1580 and 1500 cm^{-1} and λ_{\max} (EtOH) 284 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.74), 256 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.0) and 224 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1).

Analytical data :

Found : C, 71.89%, H, 6.91%, N, 6.45%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}$: C, 71.88%, H, 6.90%, N, 6.48%.

Preparation of 1-formyl-8-hydroxy carbazole(VI) :

The crude product obtained in the previous step was dissolved in dry xylene (50 ml). To this solution a solution of DDQ (5 g) in dry xylene (20 ml) was added gradually. A green precipitate of the hydroquinone immediately appeared. After the addition, the whole content was refluxed for 20 hours and then filtered to separate the hydroquinone formed. The filtrate was concentrated and then chromatographed over silica gel when petroleum ether-benzene mixture (3 : 1) eluent on concentration and crystallisation from petroleum ether gave pure yellow crystals of 1-formyl-8-hydroxy carbazole(VI), m. p. 120°, ν_{\max} (nujol) 3400-3440, 1685, 1600, 1590, 1500, 760, 730 cm^{-1} and λ_{\max} (EtOH) 311 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.2), 289 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.65), 280 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.55), 251 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.37) and 220 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.4). Yield 50%.

The p.m.r. spectrum (90 MHz) of the compound in CDCl_3 showed the presence of $-\text{NH}-$ proton (δ 10.27, s, 1H) and $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{CHO}$ protons (δ 10.00, broad singlet, 2H, one proton disappeared on D_2O exchange) and aromatic protons at C_8 and C_6 (δ 7.52, quartet, 2H) and aromatic proton at C_2 (δ 8.3, d, $J=8\text{Hz}$, 1H) and other three aromatic protons at C_4 , C_5 and C_7 (δ 8.15, d, $J=7.5\text{Hz}$, 1H; δ 7.85, d, $J=7.5\text{Hz}$, 1H and δ 7.3, d, $J=7\text{Hz}$, 1H).

Analytical data :

Found : C, 73.7% ; H, 4.3%, N, 6.65% Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}$: C, 73.92% ; H, 4.29% ; N, 6.63%.

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Synthesis of Coumarins (2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyrans) and Benzocoumarins (2-Oxo-2H-1-naphthopyrans)

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SYNTHESIS of coumarins, thiocoumarins and carbostyrils have been reported^{1,2} from cinnamoyl derivatives of phenols, thiophenols and anilines with anhydrous aluminium chloride. Phenyl cinnamates furnish either coumarins or dihydrocoumarins depending on the solvents employed. With tetrachloroethane, only dihydrocoumarins^{3,4} have been isolated, whereas, employing chlorobenzene as a solvent gave coumarins¹.

We intend to report in the present paper, the synthesis of coumarins following an analogous pathway as earlier reported^{1,2}. The corresponding intermediates-phenyl and naphthyl furylacrylates required in the synthesis, were obtained in high yields by reacting phenols and naphthols with furylacrylic acid in the presence of phosphoryl chloride and a base. These esters were then cyclised with anhydrous aluminium chloride in chlorobenzene to furnish the desired coumarins and benzocoumarins.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected.

Phenyl furylacrylates : The corresponding phenol (0.065 mole) and furylacrylic acid (0.07 mole) was dissolved in 70-80 ml pyridine. Solution was cooled to 10° and POCl_3 (4 ml) added dropwise with stirring. After the addition of POCl_3 , the mixture was stirred for 2 hrs at room temperature and then poured into cold, dil. HCl. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with water and triturated with 2N NaHCO_3 , filtered and washed with water. The product was then crystallized from ethanol to give yields varying between 90-95% (Table 1).